

Chapter 4: The drivers of the sustainable use of wild species^{1,2}

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¹ This is the final text version of Chapter 4 from the Assessment Report on the Sustainable Use of Wild Species. A laid-out version of the full assessment report will be made available in the coming months.

² Authors are listed with, in parentheses, their country or countries of citizenship, separated by a comma when they have more than one; and, following a slash, their country of affiliation, if different from that or those of their citizenship, or their organization if they belong to an international organization. The countries and organizations having nominated the experts are listed on the IPBES website.

List of supplementary materials

Appendix I - Regional Snapshots of Poverty (section 4.2.3.5. Social inequality and poverty, p. 154).

Appendix I - Regional Snapshots of Poverty.

- **East Asia and Pacific:** The incomes of the poorest 40% of the population grew on average 4.7% between 2010 and 2015. East Asia not only had the largest reductions in extreme poverty, but also in the proportion of people living on less than \$3.20 and \$5.50 per day. While extreme poverty is very low, the region saw a higher percentage of people lacking access to sanitation.
- **Europe and Central Asia:** Many countries in the region suffered setbacks in the growth of incomes of its bottom 40. On the other hand, several economies whose bottom 40 suffered large declines because of the financial and the debt crises were recovering. Among developing regions, Europe and Central Asia had the lowest percentage of people living under the 3.20 and 5.50 United States Dollars poverty lines. However, in the share of people lacking schooling enrollment, it performs less well than either East Asia and Pacific or Latin America and the Caribbean.
- **Latin America and the Caribbean:** The region saw less shared prosperity from 2010 to 2015 than in previous years as its economies were impacted by a slowdown in global commodity prices. The region had almost 11% living on less than 3.20 United States Dollars a day and over 26% on less than 5.50 United States Dollars a day in 2015. Poverty in non-monetary dimensions such as lack of access to drinking water, adequate sanitation or electricity was much less associated with monetary aspects.
- **Middle East and North Africa:** Even though the region saw an increase in the number of people living on less than 1.90 United States Dollars a day, levels of extreme poverty remained low. However, the region had more people living on less than 5.50 United States Dollars per day in 2015 than in 1990. Additionally, almost one in seven people lacks adequate sanitation.
- **South Asia:** the region saw impressive growth of the incomes of its bottom 40 between 2010 and 2015. Despite a 35-percentage point decline in extreme poverty between 1990 and 2015, the region registered only an 8% decrease in people living on less than 3.20 United States Dollars a day, and over 80% of the region still lived below 5.50 United States Dollars per day in 2015. Also, the number of people in the region living in households without access to electricity or adequate sanitation was far greater than those living in monetary poverty.
- **Sub-Saharan Africa:** A third of the countries in the region experienced negative income growth for the bottom 40% of their populations. The region with the largest number of extreme poor, Africa saw its population nearly double between 1990 and 2015, with one of the largest increases in population being for those living on less than 3.20 and more than 1.90 United States Dollars. The poor suffered from multiple deprivations such as low consumption levels and lack of access to education and basic infrastructure services.